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Interpretative function of phraseological units with a zoonymic component in the linguistic image of the world (based on the material of the English language)

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Abstract. The paper explores the least studied and, thus, the most disputable and variable aspect in describing phraseological units, which is semantics. The research is based on the semantic and grammatical analysis of 514 phraseological units with a zoonymic component in the English language collected by means of continuous sampling from the English-Russian phraseological dictionaries by professor A.V. Kunin. By analyzing lexicographical definitions, realization of the units in speech, and, in some cases, etymological aspects, we have managed to develop a hierarchy of semes in the structure of their meaning and make up a classification based on a semantic-grammatical principle. This is an essential part in the long process of compiling a dictionary of phraseological units.

KEY WORDS: paper, seem, such as, discipline, process, essential

Phraseology is now a rapidly developing sphere of language study. It tends to play a central role in a wide range of linguistic disciplines such as lexicography,

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contrastive linguistics, psycholinguistics, foreign language learning and teaching, and natural language processing. Phraseological units represent the most colourful and expressive part of any language vocabulary. Nowadays much attention is paid to defining a clear borderline between free word combinations and phraseological units, to classifying phraseological units on the basis of their semantic and/or grammatical characteristics, to corpus-based analysis of phraseology, and computational approach to lexicographical description and translation of phraseologisms. Semantic aspects of phraseological study have always been of great interest to both Russian and foreign scholars. The analysis of the latest publications and studies in the problematic sphere shows that there is a definite tendency to semantic-grammatical and lexicographical description of phraseological units in one (mainly, native) language and its dialectal variations and lexicographical and comparative description of phraseological units in two or more languages regardless of their genetic relationship. Prof. Mokienko V.M. together with other lexicographers of Saint Petersburg University implement the concept of a complete dialect dictionary in a new interpretation where dialect phraseology will be presented against a nationwide phraseological background through the use of the material of fiction, folklore, media text, slang dictionaries, records of modern speech and survey data [1]. Maria Stefanescu and Doris Sava, both dealing with the Romanian language, consider it imperative to create modern phraseological dictionaries that would be more reliable and user-friendly than the

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existing works [2, 3]. Scholars of Kazan Federal University have recently managed to enunciate the general principles of compiling a dictionary of phraseological antonyms as well as the principles of lexicographical description of phraseological antonyms for both the monolingual and bilingual dictionaries [4]. After Prof. Lebedinskaya V.A., in our research we identify phraseological units as independent nominative language units that differ from words or free word combinations and are characterized by having such features as relative syntactic stability and invariability (no word can be substituted for any component of a phraseological unit without destroying its sense), semantic unity (they convey a single concept and their meaning is idiomatic and in most cases figurative, i.e. it is not a mere total of the meanings of their components), multiwordness (they have a structure of two or more separate components), and integrated reproductivity in speech (they are not created in speech but used as readymade units) [5]. The objective of the paper is to present the results of the current stage of our research which, in general, aims at semantic-grammatical classification and lexicographical description of phraseological units with various components. One of the most productive components used in the structure of phraseological units is the one naming animals, or zoonym. The survey of the latest research shows that phraseological units with zoonymic components are widely studied in different languages. Russian scholars in cooperation with their foreign colleagues conduct a detailed study of phraseological units with various zoonymic components in

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Russian, German, English, Italian, Spanish, Chechen, Chinese, and Thai languages to disclose the cultural impact on the cognitive concepts in languages with different range of genetic relationship [6-10]. The relevance of further detailed studies of phraseological units with zoonymic components arouses little doubt, since zoo-phraseologisms are widely used among native speakers and their adequate interpretation and translation are required in a vast majority of cases to avoid misunderstanding in the process of communication. This article conveys the classification based on the semantic and grammatical analysis of 514 phraseological units with zoonymic component in the English language collected by means of continuous sampling from the English-Russian phraseological dictionaries by Prof. Kunin A.V. [11]. They can be divided into six major semantic-grammatical classes: object phraseological units – 209 units (41%), processual – 198 units (38%), attributive-predicative – 80 units (15.5%), qualitativeadverbial – 21 units (4%), modal – 7 units (1.4%), and quantitative – 1 unit (0.1%). Within the given survey we are going to present the semantic classification of object phraseological units.

2 Results and Discussion

In the sphere of phraseology the semantic categories of animacy and person are closely connected with the reality. Our classification is based on the opposition “animacy vs. inanimacy” that reveals the division of the reality into the worlds of animate and inanimate things. The category of person is considered to be a distinct feature of phraseological units identifying the man. Thus, the group of object

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phraseological units with subcategorical meanings of animacy and person includes anthroponyms while those with subcategorical meanings of animacy and non-person include units nominating animals and mythical creatures. The group of object phraseological units with subcategorical meanings of inanimacy and non-person include three subgroups of phraseological units denoting a) substances, b) concrete things, and c) abstract phenomena. Within each subgroup there can be distinguished individual subsubcategories. Nouns and adjectives play a major role in building up the semantics of phraseological units with zoonymic component in English. Nouns being major grammatical components supply the semantic structure of phraseological units with the categorical seme of objectness and subcategorical semes of animacy / inanimacy and person / non-person. Other grammatically subordinate components supply group and individual semes deserves such treatment”;; the big bad wolf “threatening or sinister person or thing”, etc. The main grammatical component is usually expressed by such zoonyms as horse, cow, duck, fly, wolf which supplies the semantic structure of phraseological units with the categorical seme of objectness and subcategorical semes of animacy / inanimacy and person / non-person. Let us see how the semantic features are revealed in speech. For example, “Tories... regard rent, interest and profit as sacred cows to be fattened at the expense of the people” (‘Daily Worker’, Nov. 25, 1961). In the given example the categorical seme of objectness and subcategorical semes of animacy (to be fattened) and non-person

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(rent, interest and profit) are clearly manifested making the statement highly expressive. 2.2 Units denoting living creatures About half of all the object phraseological units with zoonymic components (101 units in total) denote living creatures. The analysis of their lexicographical definitions and contextual realization showed that they can be classified into three semantic clusters: 1) units nominating people, or “anthroponyms” 2) units nominating animals; 3) units nominating mythical creatures. 2.2.1 Units nominating people Having the subcategorical seme of animacy, object phraseological units with zoonymic components name a person in the vast majority of usages. There have been distinguished 90 units denoting people. They tend to be called “anthroponyms”, or according to terminology of Prof. Ratushnaya E.R. they can be called “anthroponominations” [12]: a dirty dog “a low and sneaky person”;; a willing horse “a person prepared to work hard”;; a wolf in sheep’s clothing “a dangerous person pretending to be harmless”;; a bull in a china shop “an extremely clumsy person”;; a fighting cock “a pugnacious person”;; a big bug “an important person”;; a fish out of water “one who does not feel comfortable in a new environment”, etc. Phraseological units nominating a group of people or a unity can also be found within this semantic cluster: Kilkenny cats “people who fight relentlessly till their end”;; birds of a feather “people who are similar in character”;; a hen party “a group of women at a party for a woman who is going to get married soon”, etc. The grammatically main component is expressed by a zoonym that, due to its

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direct lexical meaning, forms the categorical and subcategorical semantics of the whole phraseological unit. The subcategorical seme of the person is manifested in the semantic structure of a unit to identify a human being characterized by some definite features.

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